

Middle East University
Faculty of Business Administration

COOPERATION BETWEEN NON-GOVERNMENTAL
ORGANIZATIONS AND OTHER PARTIES FOR
BETTER COMMUNITY SERVICE

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Business Administration

by

Dona Nakhle

September 2015

THESIS ABSTRACT

Master of Business Administration

Middle East University

Faculty of Business

Title: COOPERATION BETWEEN NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS
AND OTHER PARTIES FOR BETTER COMMUNITY SERVICE

Researcher: Dona Nakhle

Advisor: Ghalia Hamamy, PhD

Date completed: September 2015

Non-Governmental Organizations cooperate with other stakeholders to better serve the community in the presence of market and state failure. Proving this saying uses the constructivism paradigm which dictates the qualitative methodology, relying on depth interview and describing and mainly narrating separately and comparatively the case studies of Cénacle de La Lumière and the Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union.

This research showed that NGOs cooperate formally and informally continuously with other parties/stakeholders to fulfill their mission. It also shows that this cooperation improves jointly the work of NGOs and of the other parties. My conclusion is that NGOs cooperation with other parties is always a good thing. The formal or informal cooperation will better serve the community. Any form of cooperation improves the joint work of the organizations and other parties. NGOs working with other parties will better serve the community.

Keywords: Non-Governmental Organization, formal and informal cooperation, environment, asymmetry of information, theory of incomplete contracts.

COOPERATION BETWEEN NON-GOVERNMENTAL
ORGANIZATIONS AND OTHER PARTIES FOR
BETTER COMMUNITY SERVICE

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Business Administration

by

Dona Nakhle

APPROVAL BY THE COMMITTEE:

Ghalia Hamamy, PhD, Advisor

Patrizia Hongisto, Reader

Patrizia Hongisto, Faculty Dean

Date approved

CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
ABBREVIATIONS	viii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	ix
Chapter	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	6
NGOs	6
Definition.....	6
Mission and Functions of NGOs	8
Cooperation.....	9
Defining Cooperation	9
The Notion of Willingness	10
Types of Cooperation	11
The Environment and the Stakeholders	14
Complex Environment.....	15
Dynamic Environment.....	16
Complex and Dynamic Environment and Contingency Planning.....	16
Market and State Failures	18
Corporate Social Responsibility of the Private Sector	20
Summary.....	20
3. PARADIGM AND METHODOLOGY	22
The Research Paradigm	23
Constructivism Emergence.....	24
Constructivism Principles.....	25
The Qualitative Research Design	27
The In-depth Interview	28
The Case Study.....	28
The Qualitative Data Writing	29
The Description	30
The Narration.....	31
Summary.....	32

3. FIELD WORK AND FINDINGS.....	34
Cenacle de la Lumière	35
Overview	35
Relations with Other Parties.....	41
Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union.....	46
Mission and Vision.....	47
Relations with Other Parties.....	52
Summary.....	54
5. CONCLUSION.....	56
Answering the Research Questions	56
The Limitations of the Study	59
Further Study	60
REFERENCES	62
APPENDIX: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	655

LIST OF TABLES

1. The Three Main Questions of a Paradigm	23
2. A Practical Approach of Constructivism	26
3. The Five Research Positions of a Description	30
4. CDLL Achievements in 2013 and 2014	40

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Environment uncertainty matrix	17
2. The NGO for a better community service.....	21
3. The paradigm and methodology	33
4. The three core values of CDLL	36
5. The Christian Therapeutic Community	37
6. The three stages of the recovery journey	37
7. CDLL yearly spiritual concerts.....	39
8. The sources of income of CDLL in percentages	41
9. CDLL cooperation with other parties	45
10. LPHU's work.....	48
11. CDLL and LPHU activities	55
12. Cooperation between NGOs and other parties for a better community service	58

ABBREVIATIONS

CDLL	Cénacle de La Lumière
CSO	Civil Society Organization
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
LPHU	Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organization

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

At the beginning, I would like to thank God for giving me the power and patience to complete this thesis.

I would also like to address grateful thanks to Dr. Ghalia Hamamy, without whom I would have failed to complete this thesis and the Master's degree, due to her close attention, benevolence, and critical advice. My sincere gratitude and thanks also goes to Dr. Patrizia Hongisto and for their constructive comments in the process of my research.

I owe my sincere gratitude to Cénacle de la Lumière (CDLL) and Mr. Raphi Keypikian, and the Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union (LPHU) and Mr. Jihad Ismael for supporting and giving me all the needed time and information to finish this topic. I am also happy to thank the Lebanese Red Cross Organization for being my inspiration for the topic.

My appreciation also goes to everyone who helped me complete this study such as Ms. Rana Azar, my friends, my parents, and my brothers who stood patiently with me and supported me till the very end, giving me moral support and encouragement all throughout this thesis.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

In the beginning, it is worth mentioning that I am a twenty-six year old Lebanese citizen, interested in volunteering in Organizations for a better country and living situation. As a management student, and being influenced by the current situation, I found that the work of several Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in Lebanon is an interesting field to research. First, I started by asking myself: What exactly do I want to research? What main question shall I answer in my research?

Answering these questions can only be through further readings and research. After several readings, I mainly discovered that NGOs do not work by themselves. Every organization has put their goals and needs to better serve the community. Cooperation is created between them and other organizations / businesses / government, whether formal or informal, in order for them to reach their goals. Formal cooperation is written and agreed upon between the two parties; informal cooperation is this that just happen without a pre-agreement.

Also, I have discovered that NGOs can work in several fields and on many levels. Some NGOs work in the environmental field minimizing pollution and maintaining the world ecology. Some NGOs work with the human rights and rights of equality of all genders and races. Others work on keeping the workers out of abuse. Many examples can be given about a lot of NGOs working in several fields. I had to choose one field for this study. I have chosen to focus on the social field oriented to help Lebanese.

NGOs serve the community through helping the poor and the refugees. Others work on saving the addicted to drugs and to alcohol and in sustaining the handicapped. As drugs are destroying the youth in Lebanon and as there are plenty of handicapped in Lebanon due to the war and to the Israeli aggressions, and as the State is not very effective and efficient in this field, I realized that this thesis would serve these causes through shedding a bit of light on the work of such NGOs especially in the long and dark trajectory of the people suffering addiction and handicaps.

This thesis studies the cooperation between NGO and other stakeholders for a better community service. In order to do so, a theoretical background is given in chapter two which allows me to build a methodology to tackle the issue of collaboration in the context of NGOs. In order to work with such a topic, it was worthy to gather a literature review based on secondary data and on theoretical notions.

At the beginning, I visited some to define an NGO. Everybody has their definition of a Non-Governmental Organization, but I needed to research the exact definition of it. Then I started reading articles on several websites about NGOs dealing with refugees in Lebanon and how the International Red Cross and the United Nations are mainly helping out with those refugees. The International Red Cross has projects with people in the field all over the country with several camps where the Refugees are staying. The United Nations work internationally to help those people survive and to provide them with the basic needs for a living. My readings helped me to understand that the NGO cannot work by itself, no matter how big it was. Communication between the NGO and any other party is a must in order for these refugees to survive. Some articles showed the cooperation between the UN and the Lebanese government. Some showed the cooperation between the International Red

Cross and Government as well as the UN themselves. Every NGO needs the help of another party for them to achieve the goal they want.

However, I decided to research a different issue than the Refugees issue. I know that in Lebanon a major issue with young men is the addiction to drugs. I also read some information about the addiction and what it does to people. I searched for an NGO that works with such an issue. A lot of organizations in Lebanon work with it, but one NGO was found to be interesting as it cooperated with a business whereby it needed the company for it to achieve the goal with the young men. That NGO is called CDLL. It is located in Nahr Ibrahim. After calling them and making an appointment with the General Manager there, I went and had a one-to-one interview on April 17, 2014 with Mr. Raphi Keypikian. This interview gave me a clear idea of the way this organization works, how it deals with these young men, what it does, with whom it works and on what level.

After CDLL, I choose another NGO. That is when I thought about the handicapped and how studying the LPHU would be helpful to my study. I paid a visit to their location in Hamra where I met with Mr. Jihad Ismael on April 24, 2014. The information he provided was crucial for my study. He helped me a lot and completed my research.

Throughout my interviews, it was becoming clearer that this issue of collaboration is important. It was getting clear that the NGOs cannot work by themselves to better serve the community. That is when I started looking for answers to my problem statement through asking the following research questions:

RQ1: How often do NGOs reach their goal without the help of other parties?

RQ2: Is cooperation necessary between NGOs and any other organization for them to reach their goal?

RQ3: Is it better to have a formal or informal cooperation?

RQ4: How can this cooperation improve the work of an NGO or restrict it?

In order to answer these questions in my study, I had to introduce the topic, choose the literature used in my study, choose a paradigm and methodology, then talk about my field and conclude. All these will be tackled in depth in future chapters.

Chapter 2 is the Literature Review. In that chapter, I will define NGOs, clarify their formal and informal cooperation, the notion of willingness, the environment and stakeholders, the market and state failures, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

Chapter 3, or the paradigm and methodology, tackles the constructivism that dictates a qualitative methodology relying mainly on getting secondary data through the websites of CDLL and LPHU. However, secondary data is unable alone to provide answers to my research questions. Therefore, I had to collect primary data using depth interviews (qualitative technique) with the managers of these two NGOs. Relying on and analyzing secondary and primary data, helps the reader to reach the information in the field of cooperation between NGOs. This was accompanied with the case study qualitative technique through using description and mainly narration counterfactual logic or what if that cooperation did not occur.

Chapter 4 or the field studies CDLL and LPHU used all the available data to write their separate case studies and then to compare these two cases based on the following criteria: the year of foundation, location, mission, operation, financing, and relationships with other parties to better serve the community.

Chapter 5 or the conclusion summarizes the thesis. It also answers the research questions, proves the problem statement, and finally addresses the limitations and recommendations.

Nevertheless, it is worthy to mention, that this comprehensive or qualitative study relied mainly on modeling the data and information presented in each chapter. This will better inform the reader how NGOs cooperate with other parties for a better community service.

Finally, this thesis is addressed to all readers interested in the work of NGOs and especially those trying to assist the Lebanese authorities in order to overcome a major Lebanese problem which is drug and alcohol addiction. It is also addressed to readers who are interested in improving the life of Lebanese handicapped.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, I first define NGOs, their missions and functions. Chapter two clarifies cooperation and looks more deeply into the types, formalities, and informalities of this cooperation. This theoretical chapter focuses also on the notion of willingness, the environment and stakeholders, market and state failures, and CSR. The next paragraphs will provide a deeper look into this theoretical knowledge starting with NGOs.

NGOs

What is an NGO? This seems to be an easy question but the answer is not as simple since NGOs now constitute the new world through helping the society in several fields: social, relief, education, economic, etc. Therefore, the following writings will define NGOs, their missions and functions.

Definition

Before defining an NGO, let us break this expression into two main parts. The first part consists of the “Non-Governmental” and the second of the “Organization.” I will first define the organization.

An organization is a deliberate arrangement/structure of people to accomplish some specific purpose (Robbins et al., 2011). According to the Business Dictionary (2015), an organization is “a social unit of people that is structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals.” An organization meeting a certain need

or pursuing a goal can be either government or non-governmental. The focus of this study is non-governmental entities. Consequently, if we examine the definition of a Non-Governmental Organization by understanding each word separately, we will have the following: “An NGO is a group of people coming from a society, meeting together under a structure, to achieve a need or a goal in the society, without being a part of the Government” (Robbins et al., 2011). This is a first definition of an NGO. Yet, let us look at other definitions.

According to the United Nations Rule of Law (2015), “A non-governmental organization (NGO, also often referred to as "Civil Society Organization" or CSO) is a not-for-profit group, principally independent from government, which is organized on a local, national or international level to address issues in support of the public good.” Here, it is worthy to mention that several economic agents use the same public good for consumption and production purposes without affecting its characteristics as it is very close to a non-market service. Therefore, it is impossible to discriminate among its users. In addition, the consumption of a public good does not affect the possibility of its consumption by others especially if it is available nearby. Moreover, a public good usage is not exclusive. A public good might be education, public lighting of the streets and highways, etc. However, the taxes finance the public good (Guerrien, 2000).

After defining the public good, let us pursue the definition of NGOs. According to the World Bank (2015), NGOs “include many groups and institutions that are entirely or largely independent of government and that have primarily humanitarian or cooperative rather than commercial objectives. They can be private agencies in industrial countries that support international development; indigenous groups organized regionally or nationally; and member-groups in villages. NGOs include charitable and religious associations that mobilize private funds for

development, distribute food and family planning services and promote community organization. They also encompass independent cooperatives, community associations, water-user societies, women's groups and pastoral associations. Citizen Groups that raise awareness and influence policy are also NGOs.”

Therefore, all these definitions and many others eventually lead to the same purpose: this leads to the next aspect of the research which will consider their reason for existence by presenting their missions and functions.

Mission and Functions of NGOs

After defining NGOs and some of their types, let us look into their heterogeneous missions and functions according to their types. Here, it should be mentioned that each NGO is a distinguished case in its environment or society. Nevertheless, this thesis will focus on the general or main missions and functions of an NGO without being specific.

NGOs, like people, have missions to fulfill. But is it possible that all NGOs have the same mission? If all NGOs have the same job to do, then the society will have to wonder about the increase in number and the growth in size of these Organizations. That is why, we can say that each NGO has its own mission in the society, but they all fall under one idea which is helping and improving the community service (Fundsforngo, 2012).

Regarding the mission of an NGO, it should be “a broad statement or a general idea for which you are working for. Avoid trying to be very specific in this regard. When you come down to writing the objectives of your organization, you can be very specific” (Fundsforngo, 2012). That is why we can generalize the idea of mission for NGOs as it is a broad statement stating the work of the Organization.

Still, a mission does not stand alone. If an organization has a mission but is missing the function, the work will stop. So, a function is defined generally as the work or job of a unit (Fundsforngo, 2012). For example, if a person wants to go from place A to place B, then it is said that this person has a mission. To move from A to B, s/he needs a method of movement. If a car is used to move him/her from A to B, then it is said that the function of the car is moving people from one place to another. We can see that a mission of this person is not accomplished without the function of the car, and vice-versa (if that person had a car but did not know where to go). The same is applied for NGOs. They all have the mission of helping and serving a better community service, but to do so, these NGOs need to fulfill their function (Fundsforngo, 2012).

After clarifying the NGOs definitions, missions and functions, let us move now to elucidating the concept of cooperation that can be formal or informal.

Cooperation

No individual has sufficient experience, education, native ability, and knowledge to ensure the accumulation of a great fortune, without the cooperation of other people – Napoleon Hill (1937, p.148)

After looking into the definition of NGOs and their mission and function, we now will move to cooperation which is the reason behind the success of many groups. Therefore, the following paragraphs will define the cooperation, the notion of willingness, and the types of cooperation (informal and formal).

Defining Cooperation

According to Chester Barnard (1938), organizations as cooperative systems emerge when individuals have a purpose that they cannot realize individually. Hence,

cooperation is required and individuals are recruited, trained and assigned a job. Unfortunately, the human compliance to the organization and to labor is not granted. So, if humans have to cooperate, so NGOs should also cooperate to realize a better community service and therefore, the well-being of the society. Consequently, what does cooperation mean for NGOs?

Cooperation is the process of working together for the same goal. In business meaning, cooperation is the “voluntarily arrangement in which two or more entities engage in a mutually beneficial exchange instead of competing. Cooperation can happen where resources adequate for both parties exist or are created by their interaction” (Business Dictionary, 2012).

In this study, cooperation is referred to when the NGOs are engaged with another party in order to reach a better community service. For any two or many entities to work together, they both should be willing to do so, which brings us to talk about the notion of willingness.

The Notion of Willingness

Willingness is being prepared for a mission. Whenever willingness for two or more parties is present for the same mission, then cooperation would be at its best (Cooperation, 2016). To understand more, let us take the example of an employee in a company.

If the employee is satisfied with the return of his/her work at this company, s/he wills to succeed with the company's success. On the other hand, the company is rewarding this employee for his/her job, and then we can also say that the company is willing to keep this employee and help him/her succeed with its success. This shows mutual interest in the success of the company and the employee. They both depend on one another for the success, and the failure of one will result in the failure of the

other. We can say that since they both have the same willingness, their cooperation results in success. Here, we meet Barnard's ideas about cooperation (Cooperation, 2016).

In reverse to this idea, let us examine the case of another employee that does not work for the success of the company, but who is only interested in his/her own interest. He might have an influence on the success of the company, and thus might be fired, or the failure of the company will lead to him being out of work. Both cases taken into consideration, and since the willingness of the employee differ from that of the company, their cooperation resulted in a failure. Therefore, and according to Barnard again, the ultimate form of social control in any organization is achieved by instilling a common moral purpose among organizational participants based on the corporate culture. This will lead to a sustainable organizational cooperation, and happily to a greater managerial intervention and persuasion. In other words, the willingness to cooperate leads to a better organizational performance, outcome, and mission success (Cooperation, 2016).

After addressing the willingness to cooperate, we shall identify now the types of cooperation. We will mainly focus on the informal and the formal.

Types of Cooperation

Cooperation comes in many forms. Two or more can cooperate voluntarily or can be forced to do so under a contract.

As stated earlier, cooperation has many types. Mainly, for this study, we will be focusing on formal and informal cooperation, but at first, let us look into all types of cooperation that business refer to.

First, we can talk about the coerced cooperation. This happens when the parties are forced to cooperate and work together in order to achieve a goal. Second,

we have a voluntary cooperation, in which all the parties involved are in agreement and aware of the cooperation. Finally, we can talk about the unintentional cooperation, in which parties have the same interest and are aligned for the same goals. These parties do not intend to cooperate but they do so without the knowing (Cooperation, 2016).

Every company can come up with a new type of cooperation among its employees. Every partnership between two companies includes a cooperation. Every relationship needs cooperation to succeed. For NGOs, this study will focus on formal and informal cooperation which will be addressed in the section below.

Informal cooperation. Now that we have defined Cooperation in general, we need to define what is meant by informal cooperation and what the types of informal cooperation exist.

Informal cooperation is not a terminology used by the business world. In this thesis, I have incorporated the word informal meaning that the cooperation happening has an unofficial status. When saying unofficial, this means that no formal paper work is being transferred from one entity to another, no money is being paid in return for this cooperation, no official communication is happening between the entities, and the cooperation among them is purely for the benefit of the cause and nothing else (Cooperation, 2016).

This type of cooperation exists a lot in our society since any formal cooperation among the entities will lead to higher cost of work which is not wanted by these entities. You will read in the future chapters about the cooperation happening between the NGOs and the other parties for the benefit of both, without any formal work between them.

When it comes to the type of informal cooperation, several things can be stated. The human resources that one entity can share with the other without any

financial return can be part of the informal cooperation. If one entity is using the offices / equipment / land / machinery of the other entity without a return, this is also considered as informal cooperation. If one entity's actual work or product is used by the other entity in order to serve the community better, than this is also referred to as informal cooperation also (Cooperation, 2016).

Many examples can be put under this type of cooperation. Any cooperation between entities without any formal relation is classified in this thesis as an informal cooperation. Let us move now to the formal cooperation.

Formal cooperation. The other term that is referred to in this study is the formal cooperation. It occurs between two or more entities. In contrary to what was mentioned with regard to informal cooperation, formal cooperation is done through a contract. This type of cooperation is framed with a contract formed and signed between two or more entities, defining the way cooperation is done and all its forms. Renting offices in return for rent money, hiring employees in return for salaries, buying or renting equipment or product in return for a part of the profit or money are all examples of formal cooperation (Cooperation, 2016). When addressing a contract, we should mention and explain briefly the theory of incomplete contracts.

Kenneth Arrow presented first in the 1960s the incomplete contracts theory as a remedy to the information asymmetry. This theory is at the heart of the strategic behavior of economic agents working jointly through institutional links that define their actions possibility. Hence, an incomplete contract has gaps, missing provisions, and ambiguities and has to be completed (by renegotiation or by the courts). Moreover, such type of contract allows the co-contractors to have some future results open to negotiation. Unfortunately, these contracts are not free of charge as Jean Tirole identifies four types of transaction costs which consist of the unexpected contingencies costs, writing costs, implementation costs, and renegotiation costs.

However, if a contractual clause of the incomplete contract is not applicable, the contract will be renegotiated in order to avoid the very costly writing of a new contract. Because the co-contractors cannot preview all the possible ex ante trade-offs and their costs ex-post, they can write additional or annexed clauses to the main contract. Based on all these elements, we can say that incomplete contracts provide better and cheaper negotiation opportunities for the co-contractors than complete contracts. Finally, the law has provided rules that fill in the gaps of an incomplete contract (Al-Najjar, 1995; Segal, 1999).

The Environment and the Stakeholders

When addressing NGOs cooperation, we should address its environment and stakeholders/co-contractors, as an NGO does not exist alone in the world. It cooperates with other stakeholders to achieve once again the well-being of the society.

To begin with, let us first define a stakeholder. “A stakeholder is anyone with an interest in a business. Stakeholders are individuals, groups or organizations that are affected by the activity of the business. They are any constituencies in an organization’s environment that are affected by the organization’s decisions and actions. They include the employees, customers, social and political action groups, competitors, trade and industry associations, governments, media, suppliers, communities, shareholders, and unions (Robbins et al., 2011).

When it comes to the environment, the business world defines it as “The sum total of all surroundings of a living organism, including natural forces and other living things, which provide conditions for development and growth as well as of danger and damage” (Business Dictionary, 2015).

Is the environment affected by decisions taken by these stakeholders? Or are the stakeholders affected by how well the environment is doing? This will be answered in the below part of the study through the complex environment, the dynamic environment, and complex and dynamic environment and contingency planning.

Complex Environment

When we talk about a complex environment, we talk about the needs of more than one entity in this environment to be taken into consideration. For example, if two people are living together under the same roof, they should take into consideration each other's needs in order to survive in the household. This is considered complex. The decisions taken in the house should be considered for both parties and should not disadvantage one over the other.

In practice, the environment we live in is a complex environment. Each entity in the world is unique and no entity will consider an idea the same way the other entity does. The important thing is that they come up with a common ground and this uniqueness does not transform into conflict. In other words, the environmental complexity is the number of components in an organization's environment and the extent of the organization's knowledge about those components. Furthermore, the environmental uncertainty is the degree of change and complexity in an organization's environment (Robbins et al., 2011).

In this study, this complex environment is present in any cooperation done between an NGO and another party. The NGO's purpose or existence is for a purpose, not necessarily the same as the other party. When cooperation is implemented among them, they will come up with a common ground to serve the society better especially

that the environment is not only complex but also dynamic. Let us define now the dynamic environment.

Dynamic Environment

A dynamic environment consists of changing surroundings in which the agent navigates. Some argue that we cannot control the environment, and they are correct in the idea of it being changeable.

Whenever an environment changes, this means that the surroundings have changed and new procedures need to be implemented in order to cooperate with this new environment. Here, cooperation is among one self and between one another, both in purpose of meeting the changes in the environment (Langley et al., n.d.).

Complex and Dynamic Environment and Contingency Planning

Here, we come to the complex and dynamic environment together. To try to understand this more, let us go back to the example of the two people living under the same roof. After trying to find a common ground in living in the same house (A), now they have moved to house (B). Not only did the house change, but also, now they both have new grounds and new ways of handling the matter. The same is with the environment. Whenever the surroundings change, the grounds, which you had originally, also changed. How can the entities deal with this change? The answer is contingency planning.

Contingency planning is the plan created for the defense of several outcomes. Businesses usually take into consideration the complex environment and find common grounds in their plan. The successful businesses are those that take into consideration not only the complex environment, but also the dynamic one, and incorporate it in the plan, resulting in a contingent plan (Langley et al., n.d.).

The following chart (see Figure 1) adopted from Robbins et al. (2011) explains the environment and the necessity of the contingency planning.

Figure 1. Environment uncertainty matrix.

Source: Robbins, et al. (2011), p.63

This is related to the study in hand whenever the NGO tries to cooperate with the other entity in implementing the contingency plan in hand. The change in the environment can hurt the result of the NGO’s work if they are not prepared. The contingency plan is a must when it comes to cooperation with others since the complex and dynamic environment can affect the NGO as well as the other entity.

But why do we need NGOs in the first place to provide a better community service if we do have the public and private sectors? Unfortunately, it is due the market and government failure which will be studied in the following writings.

Market and State Failures

Having already talked about the environment and its effect on the businesses and their plan, now we need to talk about the market and state failures. First, we need to know what is meant by market failure. In economics, we first deal with supply, demand, and the equilibrium. The general rule says that equilibrium is met whenever supply and demand meet one another. In other words, the equilibrium is attained whenever the amount of products produced is the same as the amount of products demanded. This joins Jean-Baptiste Say's law of the market where each supply generates its own demand (AmosWeb Encyclonomic WEB*pedia, 2015).

As we have seen before, the environment is complex and dynamic. This will lead to higher supply, higher demand, lower supply, or lower demand. If one of these appears, then the equilibrium is lost. This is the market failure which is defined as not meeting equilibrium, or in other words, when the quantity supplied does not equate the quantity demanded. In theory, equilibrium is easy, but in fact, equilibrium might be just a theory.

After the market failure, the government will intervene and try to fix the situation. State failure is "when the government cannot fix this situation, and in opposition, it creates inefficiency leading to the misallocation of scarce resources (AmosWeb Encyclonomic WEB*pedia, 2015). So, for now, we have seen that market failure is due to the complex and dynamic environment as well as the theory of equilibrium, but there are several reasons behind the state Failure.

The first reason is that the government / public sector has no motive or profit. The government lack incentives in regards to its employees to improve the service or even cut the costs. In contrary, the government is overstaffed due to the political costs associated with the rate of unemployment. As for the second reason, politicians can have poor information about the type of service that should be provided in order to

correct the market failure. Politicians are more concentrating on the political ideology instead of the departments they run, and whenever they become keen on the matter they have, they are relocated into another department. The third reason is due to the fact that whenever the government is running a public service, the administration cost associated with government bureaucracy is very high. Finally, in order to get the public's approval and in return for votes in the elections, politicians may choose to go with the short term solution instead of the long term more efficient solutions (AmosWeb Encyclonomic WEB*pedia, 2015).

In order to overcome such failure, the government can easily find solutions for the above problems. Some solutions can consist of financial incentives to government employees to motivate them to perform better. Moreover, whenever a politician has no knowledge about the department s/he is responsible for, s/he can always employ consultants from the private sector to make decisions about how to cut costs and run the department.

Unfortunately, the government failure is one of the main reasons behind the success of NGOs. Whenever the equilibrium in the market is not attained, and the government fails to correct such problem, an NGO will have a big part in the solution of this problem (Economic Help, 2015).

Nevertheless, companies can overcome both market and government failure through the help of NGOs and CSR. However, the idea of Corporate Social Responsibility is directly related to my study as it can be a reason behind the cooperation of entities in the private sector with NGOs. This concept is detailed in the next section.

Corporate Social Responsibility of the Private Sector

According to the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO, 2012), “Corporate Social Responsibility is a management concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders.”

Social and environmental concerns are related to the work of an NGO. Whenever the concept of CSR is added by contract to any entity in the public sector, it is mandatory that they cooperate with an NGO related to this issue. For example, let us consider a company that has a lot of papers that go to waste. If they decide that they are responsible for the environment and the waste allocation, then they are socially responsible and will have to recycle. Here comes the job of the NGO. This company will have to search for an NGO having the funds to deal with waste papers and recycling and to cooperate with it for a better community service.

This cooperation will meet the needs of the company which has incorporated social responsibility into its management and thus gained the trust of the market. This also will meet the need of the NGO which is now closer to attaining the target, in this case, being the proper allocation of waste (UNIDO, 2012).

Summary

An NGO is a non-government part organization with a deliberate arrangement/structure of people or a civil and non-for profit civil society organization. It tackles the public good to achieve a social need necessary to improve the community service and therefore, its well-being. Moreover, each NGO has a mission or a broad statement stating its work accompanied with a function (s). However, an NGO does not exist alone in its environment which is complex, dynamic, and uncertain. It is surrounded by stakeholders and it should have the will to

cooperate voluntarily, through coercion, or unintentionally with them to achieve its mission and functions. This cooperation could be informal or formal through an incomplete contract.

Nevertheless, an NGO achieves the well-being of a society especially because of the State failure as the State cannot does not have some times the adequate products and services to serve the community. Based on the literature review, the following self-made flow chart (see Figure 2) will visualize the importance of the NGO.

Figure 2. The NGO for a better community service.

Once the theoretical board was set for NGOs work, we have to examine now how they do practically realize a better community service. To reach this stage, we have first, like in every research to define a paradigm and a methodology. This is the goal of the next chapter.

CHAPTER 3

PARADIGM AND METHODOLOGY

Here, we can mention that the literature review discussed in the previous chapter defined NGOs, their missions and functions. In addition, it focused on cooperation and its types, on the notion of willingness, the environment and the stakeholders, market and state failures, and CSR. This chapter will focus on the research paradigm, the methodology it dictates and its tools and ways of composing the data to move to information.

However, cooperation between NGOs and other parties in order to provide a better service for the community is the problem statement of this thesis. It is studied through asking four research questions:

- RQ1: How often do NGOs reach their goal without the help of other parties?
- RQ2: Is cooperation necessary between NGOs and any other organization for them to reach their goal?
- RQ3: Is it better to have a formal or informal cooperation?
- RQ4: How can this cooperation improve the work of an NGO or restrict it?

Chapter 2 or the literature review has given the framework for answering these four research questions. Nevertheless, the governing paradigm and methodology helping in answering these research questions are presented in this chapter.

The Research Paradigm

“A paradigm is a way of looking at the world. It is composed of certain philosophical assumptions that guide and direct thinking and action” (Cresswell & Clark, 2007, p.7). Moreover, a paradigm is also viewed as “a set of basic beliefs that deals with ultimate or first principles. It represents a worldview that defines for its holders the nature of the world, the individual’s place in it, and the range of possible relationships to that world and its parts” (Guba & Lincoln, 1989, p. 107).

Usually, when addressing a paradigm, we do have three main questions: the ontological, the epistemological, and the methodological (See Table 1).

Table 1

The Three Main Questions of a Paradigm

Question	Explanation
Ontological	It questions the form and nature of reality and, therefore, what it there that can be known about it?
Epistemological	It questions the nature of the relationship between the knower or would-be knower and what can be known?
Methodological	It questions about how can the inquirer (would-be knower) go about finding out whatever he or she believes can be known?

Source: Adapted from Guba and Lincoln (1989)

In the light of these paradigm definitions and in order to answer the four research questions and therefore, the problem statement, I rely on secondary data retrieved from the Internet about NGOs way of operation and cooperation. As

necessary secondary data provided a better glance about NGOs but was not enough, primary data was needed. Hence, it was collected through interviews. Both secondary and primary data were gathered, processed, analyzed, and synthesized to reach information that was presented through case studies. Proceeding this way was similar to assembling the jigsaw pieces without having the final picture in front of our eyes. This means that the working on the field was necessary to have a deeper knowledge about how NGOs operated and cooperated and therefore, to retrieve the literature review that was not clear without the field. This way of working is in the spirit of constructivism, the most appropriate paradigm of this thesis. So, how did constructivism emerge and what does it epistemologically mean?

Constructivism Emergence

Thomas Kuhn (1959) addressed the contrast between convergent and divergent thinking which both were central to the progress of science. Scientists use most of the time the convergent thinking in their research projects. This makes of the researcher a puzzle solver and not an innovator. Therefore, the convergent thinking does not produce fundamental discoveries or revolutionary changes in scientific theory. As a matter of fact, the scientists are students who cannot develop divergent-thinking abilities because their education is based on textbooks, inhibiting thus concrete problem solution (Riegler, 2012).

Regarding the divergent method, it allows according to Kuhn (1959) to assimilate new discoveries and theories where the scientist rearranges the intellectual and manipulative equipment s/he previously relied upon. This leads the scientist to discard some elements of his/her prior beliefs. Hence, the continuous integration of new information into pre-existing structure, the transformation of existing structure, and the construction of new ones that are based on experience to accomplish

assimilation lead to Kuhn's constructivist philosophy. Based on Kuhn's constructivist thinking, Ernest von Glasersfeld founded radical constructivism in the 1970s.

It is worthy to mention that constructivism is not a homogeneous paradigm among its thinkers. Consequently, instead of saying "Constructivism", it would be better to say "constructivist approaches" which include radical constructivism, social constructivism, and constructionism, etc.

In this regard, the constructivist approaches refer to the idea that the mental world or the experienced reality is actively constructed or brought forward and that the observer plays a major role in the theory. Nevertheless, these approaches cover neural networks, cognition, learning, living systems, organizations, architectural design, sociology, literary sciences, media sciences, and systemic family therapy (Riegler, 2012).

After addressing the emergence of this paradigm, let us divulge in the next paragraphs its principles and used methodology.

Constructivism Principles

According to Guba and Lincoln (1989, p.111), constructivism is studied through the ontology, the epistemology, and the methodology. The ontology is relativist where realities are apprehendable in the form of multiple, intangible mental constructions, socially and experientially based, local and specific in nature, and dependent for their form and content on the individual persons or groups holding the constructions. Nevertheless, constructions are more or less informed and/or sophisticated these constructions are also alterable like their associated realities. When it comes to the epistemology, it is transactional and subjectivist because the investigator and the object of investigation are assumed to be interactively linked so that the findings are literally created as the investigation proceeds (Cresswell &

Clark, 2007). Finally, the methodology is hermeneutical and dialectical where the individual constructions can be elicited and refined only through interaction between and among investigator and respondents. Therefore, “the methodology is primarily qualitative” (Cresswell & Clark, 2007, p.11).

According also to Guba and Lincoln (1989, p.112), constructivism can be studied in a more practical way through this constructed table. (See Table 2)

Table 2

A Practical Approach of Constructivism

Item	Explanation
Inquiry aim	Understanding and reconstruction
Nature of knowledge	Individual reconstructions uniting around a consensus
Knowledge	Constructed through accumulating more Informed and sophisticated reconstructions > Explicit experience
Goodness or quality criteria	Mainly based on trustworthiness and authenticity, and misapprehension
Values	Included-formative
Ethics	Intrinsic with a process toward revelation and they deal with specific problems
Training	Resocialization; mainly qualitative; depends also on history, values of altruism and empowerment
Accommodation	Incommensurable and the hegemony seeks recognition and input

Source: Adapted from Guba and Lincoln (1989)

Summarizing the previous epistemological jargon, the basic assumptions of constructivism are that “knowledge is socially constructed by people active in the research process, and that researchers should attempt to understand the complex world of lived experience from the point of view of the people who lived it. The constructivist paradigm emphasizes that research is a product of the values of researchers and cannot be independent of them” (Cresswell & Clark, 2007, p.16).

As the constructivism dictates mainly a qualitative methodology, I proceed to develop a qualitative research design and the corresponding tools to be used in the analytical part of this thesis.

The Qualitative Research Design

A research design communicates information about the key features of the study. We previously saw that constructivism dictates primarily a qualitative methodology, and hence, it focuses on discovering and understanding the experiences, perspectives, and thoughts of participants. Moreover, the qualitative research explores meanings, purpose, or the perception of reality (Hyatt, 1986). If we want to describe the qualitative research using the words of Denzin and Lincoln (2005, p. 3), we state:

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. At this level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them.

Consequently, this approach relies a lot on the description of interactions among participants and researchers in naturalistic settings with few boundaries. Hence, the research process is flexible and open. This interaction between the participant and mainly the researcher create results. These qualitative research results cannot be replicated nor generalized (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Finally, a qualitative methodology uses different tools of inquiries such as interview, conversation, focus

group, observation, case study. For the purposes of this thesis, we will mainly focus on in-depth interviews and on the case study. When it comes to writing the data, we will be using both description and narration.

The In-depth Interview

The in-depth interview is a one-to-one interview between a researcher and a research respondent. It is conducted about a specific topic in a chosen field. The interviewer must be highly skilled to encourage the respondent to talk freely without influencing the direction of the conversation. Probing questions are critical. Laddering is a particular approach to probing, asking respondents to compare differences between several items at different levels that produce distinctions at the attribute level, the benefit level, and the value or motivational level. As it is an individual interview, respondents are more likely to discuss sensitive topics. Finally, in-depth interviews are particularly advantageous when some unique or unusual behavior is being studied (Zickmund et al., 2010). For the purposes of this thesis, two interviews were conducted in 2014 with people in charge of two NGOs in Lebanon, Cénacle de la Lumière and the Lebanese Physically Handicapped Union.

The Case Study

According to Yin (2004, p. 1), “compared to other methods, the strength of the case study method is its ability to examine, in-depth, a case within its real-life context”. Thus, a case study enables the researcher to investigate important topics not easily covered by other methods. Nevertheless, case studies are applied when the research addresses either a descriptive question (what happened?) or an explanatory question (how and why did something happen?). Moreover, a case study helps in understanding better a particular situation through making direct observations and collecting data in natural settings, compared to relying on derived data. Therefore, it

allows both data collection and analysis thanks to the investigator's skills and expertise in inquiry.

After addressing the importance of a case study, it would be of great importance to focus on the three basic steps of its design. The first one consists of defining the case that the researcher is studying. The second one decides if the researcher will refer to one or to multiple case studies. Finally, the third step considers if it is necessary or not to use theory development to help to select the case(s), develop the data collection, and organize the initial data analysis strategies. Moreover, a case study might use quantitative and/or several qualitative techniques such as a focus group, an interview, etc. to collect and triangulate data and to establish converging lines of evidence to have more credible findings. Furthermore, if the researcher's case study is driven by a discovery motive, such as this thesis, the analysis should start with what the researcher thinks s/he has discovered.

Finally, when it comes to composing the case study, it should alternate description and narration while using a simple and attractive style (Yin, 2004). As a matter of fact, simplicity makes beauty, and therefore, with some creativity of the researcher, the case study will "drag" the reader to read till the last letter. After having discussed the qualitative research design and its tools, the interview and the case study, it is time now to detail description and narration.

The Qualitative Data Writing

After having collected the necessary qualitative data, the researcher should treat it through using the floating attention while reading it, the coding, and finally the templating (Dumez, 2013). Writing the field part consists in this thesis of two case studies about two NGOs, CDLL and LPHU for which the secondary data was retrieved through the Internet; while the primary data was done through the interview

tool. However, writing the field part should use jointly description and narration. So what do these writing techniques mean?

The Description

According to Dumez (2013), a description has five research positions. The following table (See Table 3) will contribute to better understanding these positions.

Table 3

The Five Research Positions of a Description

Research position	Explanation
Objective description	Constructed based on the interviewees' descriptions
Correction	The researcher considers the descriptions made by actors and corrects these descriptions in order to reach a near description but not an accurate one. Yet, the diverging or contradictory descriptions of the actors might help the researcher
The description should remain the fact of the field actors	The researcher interprets these descriptions but does not undertake them.
The researcher should discard the descriptions made by the actors regarding the situations where they interact	The researcher constructs a description that does not consider the regular descriptions made by the actors
The researcher has a synoptic vision of the different descriptions	The researcher produces a knowledge effect, takes into account all the descriptions made by the actors regarding The situations they are living, and criticizes these descriptions and attempts to write corrected descriptions

Source: Adapted from Dumez (2013)

That is not all as the qualitative research considers the context and therefore the accordion effect (inflating or deflating the context) where each element of the context describes its own context, which has its own context, etc. In a case study, the description colors, gives an aesthetic aspect to the analysis as it describes the living experience of the studied actors. Consequently, the description may reject a theory and/or invent new notions. Moreover, the description is similar to a simple model reduced to some simple elements; this model is then complexified through several steps (Dumez, 2013). The following part will address the narration.

The Narration

In Dumez (2013), Tzvetan Todorov defined the narration in 1973 as the construction of a transition from one equilibrium to another. As for Ricoeur, he considered in 1980 that in a narration, the facts should follow each others' without determining each others' completely. When it comes to Dumez (2013), he asks the following question: how to construct a narration which is relatively independent of a theory which allows discussing existing theories and developing new theories? He also thinks that when processing a qualitative material, the first step in a narration is the establishment of chronologies elaborating if an event preceded another one and if it was the cause of this event or not.

After establishing chronologies, the researcher should undertake a sequential analysis having a start, a process made by successive sequences having change points, and an end. Therefore, going backwards in the past that preceded the beginning of the studied dynamic and in order to understand this beginning is called analeptics which is a must in a narration. The further step is to construct a template in which two points of view should be distinguished: that of the actors and that of the researcher.

Finally, the description and the narration are not separated. On the contrary, they are complex and complementary. However, narration is a speech; description is also a speech but could also be diagram or a figure. Therefore, the description is an instantaneous cut and it focuses on stationary or quasi stationary states while narration focuses on the change (Dumez, 2013). In simpler words, description is a still and narration is a video!

Summary

A research consists of an idea that is to be elaborated within a paradigm dictating a suitable methodology that leads to findings. Therefore, the link between the idea and the findings is the methodology, the main objective of this chapter. In order to understand how NGOs communicate with other parties to provide a better community service, this research relies on four research questions. It also uses the constructivist paradigm. Constructivism dictates a qualitative methodology using in the case of this thesis the interview and the case study to collect and analyze the data and the description and narration in order to write the findings. The following figure (See Figure 3) summarizes the main ideas of the chapter and constitutes a link to the findings chapter.

Answering the research questions in order to confirm the problem statement recalls the final step in this thesis which is the field work. Hence, the next chapter will detail the qualitative findings through describing and narrating them. The main objective is to model qualitatively the cooperation between NGOs and other parties in order to provide a better service for the community based on two NGOs.

Figure 3. The paradigm and methodology.

CHAPTER 4

FIELD WORK AND FINDINGS

After having defined NGOs, their missions, functions, and cooperation theoretically with other parties to serve better the community and after anchoring this thesis in constructivism relying mainly on two qualitative techniques which are the in-depth interviews and case studies, it is now time to see how these NGOs operate on the field.

Based on theoretical and epistemological knowledge displayed in the two previous chapters, we will now describe and narrate the case studies of two NGOs in Lebanon. Those were of great interest for me because they deal and try to attenuate two major social problems all most of the countries face.

The first one, CDLL is an Organization that deals with a huge problem in society, the addiction of young to drugs. The second Organization, the LPHU, and as the name states, deals with the problems that the handicapped in the Lebanese society face. It also tries to solve these problems and integrate these people softly into the society. In the next parts of this chapter, we will talk about each NGO by itself and how both helped me in answering the research questions of this thesis and the problem statement.

Cenacle de la Lumière

We will start by over viewing this NGO located in Nahr Ibrahim. After that we will be addressing its communication with other parties based on the CDLL website and on the interview conducted on April 17, 2014 with its General Manager Mr. Raphi Keypikian.

Overview

CDLL is a non-profit NGO founded in 2006 in order to prevent and fight youth's drug and alcohol addiction through raising their awareness and healing the suffering ones. For this purpose, it relies on a team consisting of staff and volunteers who work jointly and professionally in this regard.

When it comes to the prevention, CDLL provides the society with the appropriate knowledge to better deal with drugs, and to inspire the young men to grow wisely and fulfilling lives away from drugs. Unfortunately, when a young person becomes an addicted to drugs, CDLL starts by supporting his family first and then by trying to heal the youngsters and therefore, help them to overcome this addiction and to be reintegrated progressively in the society as responsible and productive persons leading a right way of living.

In both cases, of prevention and of healing, CDLL relies on a comprehensive recovery program, in a Christian Therapeutic Community Context. Mentioning the world "Christian" leads to the core three values of CDLL which are displayed in the self-made figure (See Figure 4).

Figure 4. The three core values of CDLL.

How does CDLL work on recovering the young addicted to drugs? In order to answer such a question, we should examine three basic elements: the Christian Therapeutic Community, the recovery journey, and the recovery objectives.

a The Christian Therapeutic Community

Recovery means several interventions at different stages for the drug addict.

The following figure will display them (See Figure 5).

Figure 5. The Christian Therapeutic Community.

Source: www.cenacledelalumiere.org

We can finally mention that this Christian Therapeutic Community is the internal approach affecting the main vision of a life for a young addict. Hence, this community helps the young to a sustained recovery through a Bio-Psycho-Social-Spiritual way. This will help the young addict later on to reintegrate productively in the society.

b The recovery journey

This journey in CDLL consists of three main stages, the admission, the residential rehabilitation, and the outpatient re-entry (See Figure 6).

Figure 6. The three stages of the recovery journey.

Source: Self-made figure based on the CDLL website (www.cenacledelalumiere.org)

Regarding the first one or the *admission*, it lasts for one month where CDLL accepts men aged between 18 and 45 years. All the candidates and their families are thus introduced into the full recovery program, objectives, stages, activities, schedules and conditions. This stage aims at motivating candidates to get out from the chaotic life and dependent behaviors. A full psychological, medical, legal, family and social assessment is performed.

As for stage two or the *residential rehabilitation*, it lasts for a longer period expanding over fifteen months. This stage offers an intensive wide scope care with various strategies aiming at abstinence from drug and alcohol use, cutting dependency cycles, encouraging a sincere relationship with Jesus Christ, building a new identity, interiorizing an organized life style, and developing the sense of responsibility, values and joy in life.

Finally, the last stage or the *outpatient re-entry* lasts for 18 months to facilitate the building up of a life project on all professional and social levels, with the objectives of maintaining abstinence and preventing relapse, resuming more independent life and higher responsibilities and being committed to a full-time job.

Let us address now the recovery objectives.

c The Recovery objectives

The recovery objectives aim at leading a right, organized and productive way of living; changing negative behaviors; and abstinence from substance abuse, free from dependency. In order to achieve such objectives, the organization has been operating since nine years. Moreover, CDLL organizes a yearly spiritual concert starting since 2007 as shown in the figure below (See Figure 7).

Figure 7. CDLL yearly spiritual concerts.

Source: Self-made figure based on the CDLL website (www.cenacledelalumiere.org)

However, the objective of these Concerts is to relay on engaging message of hope and faith that can touch the hearts of the public, promote devoted and young talents and empower them to be themselves messengers of light in our world, and raise funds to support the growing mission. Nevertheless, the 2013 and 2014 years achievements were worthy of being displayed comparatively as much as possible in the following table (See Table 4).

Table 4

CDLL Achievements in 2013 and 2014

Achievement	Year 2013	Year 2014
Sessions of professional orientation	1,057	551
Sessions of individual counseling	572	502
Consultations with the families of the beneficiaries	332	305
Messes	260	270
Group meetings and therapeutic sessions	228	112
Individual spiritual counseling	156	160
Empowerment sessions (fine arts, sports, music, relaxation)	142	125
Spiritual sessions	128	168
Support to individuals and their families	69	211
Legal consultations	42	34
Recreational indoor and outdoor activities	10	16
Spiritual retreats	10	9

Source: Self-made table based on the CDLL website (www.cenacledelalumiere.org)

In order to achieve such activities and achievements, the CDLL needed money raised mainly through donations. The following self-made figure (See Figure 8) displays comparatively these funding sources comparatively for the years 2013 and 2014. After over viewing the CDLL, it is worthy now to address its relationships with other parties.

Figure 8. The sources of income of CDLL in percentages.

Source: Self-made figure based on the CDLL website (www.cenacledelalumiere.org)

Relations with Other Parties

In CDLL, communication with the *government* is a must. They have a special relationship with the Ministry of Social Affairs. This relation is partially for financial purpose whereby they handle almost 15% of the expenses of this organization. The communication with the ministry of Social Affairs in CDLL is also to help in all events and projects they want to execute. They also have relations with the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Justice, and the National Social Security Fund. These other relationships are minor when it comes to their primary communication with the Ministry of Social Affairs, but they exist in order to help in the mission.

Other than the government, CDLL have relations with other *similar organizations*. They say that their relation with these organizations is a must as they

can benefit from them through financial help and / or direct help (human resources, first aid help, products and services, etc.) especially that the Organization offers its services for free. Furthermore, CDLL has a special and formal or contractual relationships with the *Church in Byblos*. Their mission is based mainly on the Christian beliefs, and thus, the church has adopted their mission and has helped a lot for them to reach their goal with the young men suffering from Drug Addiction. This relation helps CDLL to solve the problems in the small community these young men are coming from. The church can keep an eye on the neighborhood these men come from and in order to prevent the increase of such problems. The church plays a major role in the third stage of this program whereby the men go back to live with their families. It helps them integrate with their community and family in order for them to live a normal life away from chaos.

Last but not least, CDLL has a relation with an organization under the name “*Sanita*.” First, the offices of this NGO are placed in the building of Sanita. Furthermore, as explained by Mr. Keypikian (2014), all men that reach the stage whereby they need to integrate in society with a full time job, Sanita offers that job for these men in order for them to reach the final stage of the program. *This communication between these two parties is not formal between them, but it is written* in all the reports presented to the Ministry of Social Affairs. This communication between these two parties in this special case is easier than in any other case as the president of CDLL, Ms. Souraya Frem, is the daughter of the CEO of Sanita, Mr. Badih Frem.

Furthermore, the center where these men live in is not owned by the Organization. This center is owned by “*Télé-Lumière*,” which has donated its property for CDLL with no return of money.

Now, what about the formal and informal cooperation of CDLL?

a Formal cooperation

As stated in Chapter 2, formal cooperation is set to be cooperation under a contract. Also, as stated earlier, we can say that *CDLL has a formal relation with the church in Byblos*. Being a Non-Governmental Organization and a Church, this relation is set to have no financial profit. This contractual formal relationship is only present because the result of such relation helps both ends in reaching their goal.

When CDLL cooperated with the *Church* for a better society of men, free of drugs and alcohol addiction, CDLL is reaching its goal and further coming to better community. On the other hand, when the church knows that CDLL helps these men through a Christian therapeutic process, it is also reaching its goal, if we may mention it as a goal, as young men are meeting Jesus and learning the true meaning of Love and Faith.

It is also important to mention that all communication and cooperation done with the *Government*, especially the *Ministry of Social Affairs*, are considered as formal relation. These relations are legally forced on the organizations in Lebanon. Any activity or event that needs to be done is one that has an impact on the society and the public, which is why the government needs to be notified of formally to enable them to provide the security to the event.

When asked about the Cooperation with the government, Mr. Keyplikian (2014) answered, “It is important to stay under the law and notify all necessary parties of the activities done by the Organization to ensure the continuity and improvement of CDLL.”

Now, what about the informal cooperation of CDLL?

b Informal cooperation

To remember what is meant by informal relation, and as stated earlier in chapter two, informal cooperation is created when no formal paper work is being transferred from one entity to another, no money is being paid in return for this cooperation, no official communication is happening between the entities, and the cooperation among them is purely for the benefit of the cause and nothing else.

It is clear that CDLL has an informal relation with almost all parties it works with outside the government. The two main cooperations I want to emphasize on in this part of the Chapter are the relations with *Sanita* and *Télé Lumière*.

To see the important of these two entities in the continuation of CDLL, I want to ask what if that relation did not exist. And this is a legitimate step in the narration process (Dumez, 2013).

If the center that is now donated to CDLL from Télé Lumière is not present, it would give CDLL a hard time with finding a free center for these men to live in, or it would put them under a new cost, being the cost of rent. This cooperation created between CDLL and Télé Lumière has benefited both parties. As obvious as it may be, CDLL is benefiting from Télé Lumière which has helped in reaching a better society.

Télé Lumière is a Christian entity and is based on Christian beliefs. With its cooperation with CDLL, it has come a bit closer to Christian society. That is why we can say that this informal cooperation created between these two entities is purely for the benefit of the cause and nothing else.

The second point that needs to be mentioned in this informal cooperation is the cooperation with Sanita. The third stage of recovery in CDLL is the Outpatient Re-Entry. As mentioned, this stage of the program facilitates the building up of a life project on all professional and social levels, with the objectives of maintaining

abstinence and preventing relapse, resuming more independent life and higher responsibilities and being committed to a full-time job. Sanita has allowed these men to work at its company for the benefit of a better society. It has a CSR towards its community and through this cooperation with CDLL, it has reached a part of it. On the other hand, CDLL has benefited from Sanita in this respect through finding a place for these men to work in as it may be hard for them to engage themselves into society without the help and support of the organization. Finally, it would be worthy now to sketch the relations of CDLL with other parties and to display the formal/informal cooperation (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. CDLL cooperation with other parties.

Source: Self-made figure based on CDLL website and the interview with Mr. Keypikian (2014)

Finally, the mission that CDLL is working on is truly helping the Community. CDLL has several formal and informal cooperation with the external world. This cooperation has made their mission easier and helped the other parties in the CSR they have. The formal relations are a must when it comes to the government and the governmental entities, but the informal relations are the ones that have truly helped the mission of both entities to reach the goals in a better way.

Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union

The case study of the LPHU in located Hamra will be consisting of an overview of the NGO. This includes its mission and vision and relations with other parties through collecting secondary data of its website and primary data through an interview with its President, Mr. Jihad Ismael. Let us start by over viewing this NGO.

Overview

The Lebanese Physical Handicapped Union (LPHU) is a non-Governmental, Non-profit Organization that was founded in 1981 by handicapped people. Their concern was to order to reach their rights as prescribed in International Laws and thus, setting equality between the handicapped and non-handicapped opportunities in life. It consists of about 1,200 members that are physically handicapped; thousands are supporting their mission as well as volunteers and friends. The geographical scope of this organization is throughout the Lebanese boundaries as well as in the Arabic world for the incorporation of the Handicapped in the decision making and to focus on the legal rights of these handicapped in the society as to move them from segregation to integration.

The LPHU has focused during the past decade on the application of the Lebanese Law 220/2000 that states the fundamental rights of the handicapped,

especially the rights to accessing, the right to a proper work, education and learning, political and civil rights, as well as the rights to be in social activities. The union has had ongoing campaigns, mainly the Ongoing Campaign Demands, translated through several projects and time periods that can serve the application of the law. Now, what about the mission and vision of this NGO?

Mission and Vision

The LPHU believes that the evolution in the society does not happen unless the society is built on the respect of human rights, social justice, solidarity, and equality. They believe that the community should give opportunities to all its citizens according to the skills and potential of each citizen in order for them to be a part of the decision making locally and internationally for the benefit of all. The union works on defending the rights of the handicapped as well as their rights to be granted equal opportunities and quality of life (health, education, employment, social, and freedom of opinion). LPHU also seeks to spread the culture of integration and participation, never leaving the idea of having the disability issues as a main part of the human rights.

The LPHU's work is based on two major components: Logistical and Human Rights work from one hand and the Community Development Projects from the other hand. This way, they can raise awareness on the importance of the Handicapped rights as human rights in the integration in society, and can include physical rehabilitation, educational integration, economic integration, vocational rehabilitation, community outreach, inclusive development in the society. In order to fulfill such a mission, LPHU adopts National Campaigns, Projects Translating Rights, and Human Rights Development Projects. Let us detail each of these elements (See Figure 10).

Figure 10. LPHU’s work.

Source: Self-made figure based on LPHU website (www.lphu.com)

a. National Campaigns

The LPHU has managed many campaigns throughout the years and has participated in the enforcement of many laws regarding the equality of humans and integration of the handicapped in the society. Below, I will be mentioning only two of their main campaigns, one which the union has lead and the other which the union participated in.

The first is “My Rights” which deals with the political rights of the handicapped and their rights to have a proper environment when voting. This campaign was lead by the LPHU. Through this campaign, the LPHU have concluded

the issuing of the Law 220/2000 which provides the proper environment for the handicapped to vote.

The second campaign, “No for War”, in which the union has participated in, deals with the conflict that the politicians have over the country and how these conflicts are affecting the whole situation in Lebanon. Let us detail each of these two campaigns.

i. Haqqi” (My Right) Campaign

This is a National Campaign which has started in 2005 for the implementation of the political rights of the handicapped. It has proposed the integration standards through the election process. This campaign was formed through collection of the candidates’ signatures on the parliamentary forum for the rights of the handicapped, as well as awareness campaigns on the integrated election process. After the 2005 elections in Lebanon, this same campaign continued throughout the summer of 2007 sub-elections. It has reopened the same ideas with the help of the Ministry of Interior to prepare for the 2009 and 2010 elections for these to have a full integration process for the handicapped. This campaign went through all the election stations in Lebanon to provide a minimum environment for the integration process. Finally, this campaign concluded the issuing of the Law 220/2000 facilitating the election process for the handicapped.

ii. “No for War” Campaign

The main focus of this campaign is to strengthen the civil peace and citizenship in the country. The idea of this campaign goes back to the 1980s, where Lebanon was under the state of war, but continued mainly in May 2008 where the main slogan was “If you don’t agree, don’t come back” for the

politicians that met in Doha, Qatar, under the title of communication for the fate of Lebanon. The Union has participated in Sit-ins, meetings, and press conferences against the civil war that is remembered every year on April 13. Let us move now to the next part which is the Projects Translating Rights.

b. Projects Translating Rights

Other than the National Campaigns, The LPHU has had many projects that translated the rights of the handicapped. Same as the campaigns, I will be talking only about two projects. The first project, lead by the LPHU, focused on the socio-economic integration of the handicapped, and it resulted in recruitment offices that received applicants from these people with disabilities. The second project, in which the LPHU participated in along with several other organizations, under the title “Lebanon Citizen”, resulted in several groups that are fighting for the law of integration of the handicapped in the political process. The following writings will detail these two projects.

i. Socio-economic integration of persons with disabilities

This project is a typical experience in Lebanon and the Arab World, aiming at the integration of the disabled people to develop economically and socially. In order for any disabled human to develop in such areas, they need to focus on the career and skill development from one end, and the awareness of the society on the other end. The union has had several campaigns for employers and the society for the importance of the integration of the handicapped in jobs and the capabilities of these disabled in the workplace.

The Union also worked with the Private sector on the social diversity concept through establishing the “Body Supporting Diversity in the

Workplace” and through spreading of the concept of “Friendship between the Disabled and Corporations” Further to the private sector, the Union has also worked with the Public Sector through awareness in colleges, universities, local, and civil society. This project covers four provinces and has resulted in the creation of employment offices in Kornish Al Mazraa - Beirut, Bar Elias - Bekaa, and Tyre – the South.

ii. “Lebanon Citizen” Project

This project aims at enabling the participation of the Lebanese Citizen in the political decisions through providing the knowledge and skills that relate to the legal operation and democratic principles, and strengthening the concept of citizenship and advocacy. The Union has undertaken the Public Awareness Work in Beirut, while six other organizations have done the same among other regions of Lebanon. They are working with groups consisting of twenty-five to four hundred citizens having different political concepts. These groups hold awareness campaigns as the first stage, to move to the second stage later on, being the implementation of the work in socio-economic issues. Now, what about the Human Rights Development Projects?

b. Human Rights Development Projects

The Union does not only work on the Handicapped rights, but human rights in general. They have worked equally on projects and studies all over the country since 2009, such as the Center for Disability Support in Tyre and Mashghara; The Initiative in monitoring the Disability in Lebanon; and The Social Responsibility in Lebanon. Other projects were also combining the Development and Rights and in the next part

of the study, I will be talking about two of these projects which are the Vocational Training Project and the Disability Support Center in Baalbeck.

i. Vocational Training Project

This project works in parallel with the socio-economic integration project. The union has organized intensive courses in vocational and technical training, English Language, Computer skills, Specialized computer programs. This has initiated in the branches of the union all over Lebanon and then moved to several areas such as the town of Srifa and the city of Bint Jbeil.

ii. Disability Support Center in Baalbeck

The disability support center covers all the northern Bekaa Area. LPHU launched the center ex post the 2006 war on Lebanon to cover some of the urgent and direct needs of the Lebanese citizens through being a mediator between those needing help and those wanting help. This center has worked on completely removing the need for help in the area and for the disabled people.

After that, the center has moved to the second stage of its work, being the Social Development in association with all existing projects for a better socio-economic integration in the Baalbeck – Hermel Region. Now what about the relations with other parties?

Relations with Other Parties

As clear as it may be, the LPHU has relationships with the majority of the entities in the country. Their projects are always supported by other organizations, and they support other organization's projects. Their campaigns are directed towards

the private and the public sector. They have worked with several Ministries and still work with them. Some of their relations are formal, while some others are informal.

a. Formal

Although their relations are numerous and their work is depending on the society, no formal relation was created between them and any other party. Same as CDLL, this organization has legal obligations towards several ministries when doing campaigns and projects, and their relation with the ministry of Justice as the ministry stipulates for the implementation of the rights always has a legal form such as a memorandum of understanding or a contract, but to have a formal relation with any of the surroundings, this was not shown clearly.

When I asked about a formal relation, Mr. Ismael (2014) replied: “If by formal you mean written, then no. None of our relations are formal. We believe that written relations with NGOs is not necessary. When we have something we believe in and are working for, we do not need written formal communication.”

b. Informal

As for informal cooperation, the LPHU has clearly shown cooperation with several of the NGOs around them in several projects and campaigns. An informal cooperation has formed Friendships among the organizations and the people working in these organizations. The sentence that Mr. Jihad Ismael (2014) said above shows clearly that NGOs do work for the benefit of the society and the cooperation between each other is always for the community benefit. All cooperation that happens between the LPHU and the entities around them are said to be informal and have helped all these entities to reach a better community, and is still doing so.

Finally, when I asked Mr. Ismael about the necessity of the relations with other entities of the society, he has replied “Nothing will ever stop us from working

towards a better society, but surely without the help of the organizations and the financial support of all the donors, our work will be harder.”

His answer concludes the above case. After knowing the LPHU and going deeper through its work, we can now say that this too cannot work by itself. It always needs the support of the surroundings and the help of the government and the society.

Summary

NGOs exist and cooperate formally and informally with several governmental and non-governmental entities in order to better serve the community. This chapter focused on two NGOs namely CCDLL preventing and fighting youth's drugs and alcohol addiction and the LPHU working in order to reach equal opportunities in life for handicapped people when it comes to non-handicapped.

The following self-made figure (See Figure 11) based on what was reported in this chapter compares both NGOs and allows sketching a little conclusion of this chapter. Figure 11 shows that NGOs are here to serve sincerely some human purposes in order to improve the lives of Lebanese / residents in Lebanon. This means having a better standard of living. Nevertheless, these organizations cannot succeed in serving the community without the formal and especially the informal cooperation with other parties namely NGOs.

The next chapter or the conclusion of the thesis will summarize the previous chapters main ideas in order to answer the research questions and thus the problem statement. However, generalization is not the objective of this work anchored in constructivism.

Figure 11. CDLL and LPHU activities.

Source: Self-made figure based on what was written previously in this chapter.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

I can now conclude this thesis with answering the research questions and confirming the problem statement. I will be, stating the limitations, and finally the recommendations of this research.

Answering the Research Questions

As stated earlier in this study, an NGO is a non-government part organization tackling the public good to achieve a social need necessary to improve the community service. Each NGO has defined their work along with their function(s). However, an NGO does not exist alone in a complex, dynamic and uncertain environment. The NGO is surrounded by stakeholders, and it should be able to cooperate formally or informally with them to achieve its mission and functions voluntarily, through coercion, or unintentionally. This cooperation is existent through an incomplete contract. Furthermore, an NGO achieves the well-being of a society because of the State failure. SCR is the main key that can be used by the private sector in order to avoid the State failure.

Having said the above, I have decided to tackle our research question through constructivism. Throughout this study, I was able to be puzzle solvers and rather than innovators. The study is primarily qualitative and has used secondary and primary data for this narration. The focus is mainly on the in-depth interviews held and the two case studies. As stated earlier, the two in-depth interviews are said to be a one-to-one interview between the researcher and the respondent. In this case, I made these

two interviews in 2014 with CDLL and the LPUH. As for the case studies, it has allowed me to define the case, decide on which and how many case studies, and then select the case(s) for the study.

Having gone to these NGOs and met with the general manager and president of CDLL and the LPUH gave me an idea about the great work these organizations do for the society. The work, that each of these organizations do, has a huge impact on the society. This work is clearly not done by working in an isolated way. This study has clearly shown that frequent and continuous cooperation is needed in the work of these organizations. This cooperation is what makes a better community and the cooperation will serve the community better.

To conclude our case studies, we can say that NGOs will have hard time reaching their goals without the help of the other stakeholders. These other stakeholders will also benefit from this cooperation and both will lead to a better community service. Sometimes, this cooperation can be a necessity for the mission of the NGO and without it; the mission would be hard to reach. As for the types of cooperation, the formal ones are shown to be mainly with the government and its ministries which have an impact on the legal side of the whole process. This legal part is always important for the NGO as it provides it with security. As for the informal relations, in the above two cases, we have seen that this type of cooperation was said to be a main pole for the work and without it; the work would have been harder if not impossible. Last but not least, it is important to state that any type of cooperation in any work, especially in an NGOs work will always improve the process and help in better service as proved in the formal and informal cooperation of CDLL and LPHU with the government, the church, other NGOs, the private sector, etc.

Now that the study is done and the more systematically research questions are answered, we can say that cooperation between NGO and other parties is a must for a better Community Service. Hence, I can summarize and model what I have said in this paragraph about how NGOs cooperate with other parties for a better community service in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Cooperation between NGOs and other parties for a better community service.

The Limitations of the Study

The constructivist paradigm is used in this research. Such a paradigm is not easy as it resembles to assembling a puzzle without the picture at hand. In addition, it dictated a qualitative methodology relying describing and mainly narrating case studies. Therefore, conducting only two case studies and two in-depth interviews is the first limitation and this is not enough at all. But, fortunately, the responsible of each of these two NGOs were kind enough to grant me an interview especially that Lebanese responsible avoid most of the times making interviews. If they do, they do not divulge an exploitable information or even data.

The second limitation is practical and it is concerned with the geographical framework of the study. As a matter of fact, as one organization was in Nahr in North Mount-Lebanon Ibrahim and the second one was in Hamra in the very crowded heart of Beirut. This means that moving several times and during the same day between CDLL and LPHU was not easy at all especially with the traffic jam and the unexpected events continuously occurring in Lebanon such as infrastructure unexpected works and insecurity events.

Moreover, the third limitation was research technical. I had to retrieve consistent information from the secondary data about CDLL and LPHU and from the primary data through the interviews I have conducted with the managers of these two NGOs. I was submerged with data. Therefore, I adopted the what if reasoning to overcome the huge bulk of data and to use only the most relevant information for this research.

Finally, a one-to-one interview is not as easy as it sounds. The interviews were of great help and source of Primary data but in this specific case the job was not easy

as the organizations were very secretive of the information held in respect of formal and informal communications.

After having answered the research questions and proved the problem statement regarding the cooperation between NGOs and other parties for a better community service, and after having stated the limitations of this study, it would be worthy to conclude with the recommendations. Below is a section for further studies that can be done in relation to this study.

Further Study

It is important to state that this thesis has tackled a very small part of the NGO world. That NGOs world will benefit from these studies on collaboration research and has a big horizon for future research. I have seen the relationship of NGOs with the other parties for a better community service, but their work is not only fixed on cooperation. The study of an NGO is still young and can further be dealt with on various levels such as the political, the economical, the institutional, the financial, and the civil society. As for me and this study, I will happily mention that tackling the four research questions stated earlier was more than satisfying and being able to answer such questions has given me a whole new area of thoughts on the Non-Governmental Organizations and their work. Here, prior to this research I only thought that NGOs communicated only among each others. But after this research, I found out that these NGOs need formal and informal cooperation among them and the other entities in order to improve their communication and thus, to better serve the community.

Nevertheless, as two case studies can never generalize the work of NGOs in serving better the community in Lebanon, it would be worthy to tackle more NGOs working in these two fields and in other social work field. This would allow the

constitution of a database in this field allowing later on to move to the pragmatist paradigm that uses jointly mixed methods. In other words, the qualitative methodology will explore the topic more in depth. While the quantitative methodology based on conducting a survey by a self-made and administered questionnaire will confirm the research findings and will allow generalizing the results of the study through using inferential statistics.

REFERENCES

- Al-Najjar, N-I. (1995). Incomplete contracts and the governance of complex contractual relationships. *American Economic Review*, 85(2), 432-437.
- Barnard, C. (1938). *The functions of the executive*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- BBC News. (2014). *Business Studies – Business Environment – Stakeholders*. Retrieved from <http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/business/environment/stakeholders1.shtml>
- Cooperation. (2012). In *Business Dictionary*. Retrieved September 28, 2016 from <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/cooperation.html>
- Cresswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2007). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2005). Introduction. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (3rd ed.; pp. 1–29). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Dumez, H. (2013). *Méthodologie de la recherche qualitative : Les 10 questions clés de la démarche qualitative*. Paris: Magnard-Vuibert.
- Environment. (2012). In *Business Dictionary*. Retrieved September 28, 2016 from <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/environment.html>
- Equilibrium. (2015) In *AmosWeb Encyclonomic WEB*pedia*. Retrieved on September 28, 2016 from http://www.amosweb.com/cgi-bin/awb_nav.pl?s=wpd
- Equilibrium. (2015). In *Economic Help*, Retrieved on September 28, 2016 from <http://www.economicshelp.org>
- Funds For NGOs. (2012). *Mission of NGOs*. Retrieved from <http://www.fundsforngos.org/free-resources-for-ngos>
- Guba, E.G. & Lincoln, Y. S. (1989). Competing paradigms in qualitative research. In N.K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research*, (pp. 105-117). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Guerrien, B. (2000). *Dictionnaire d'analyse économique microéconomie, macroéconomie, théorie des jeux, etc.* Paris, France: La Découverte.
- Hill, N. (1937). *Think and grow rich*. Washington, DC: The Ralston Publishing Co. Retrieved from <http://www.ivpp.nl/wp-content/uploads/masterminds.pdf>

- Hyatt, J. F. (1986). Spiritually, medicine, and healing. *Southern Medical Journal*, 79, 736-743.
- Kuhn, T.S. (1985). *The essential tension: Tradition and innovation in scientific research*. (pp. 105 – 165)
- Langley, P., Laird, J., & Rogers, S. (n.d.). *Cognitive architectures: Research issues and challenges*. Retrieved from Stanford University.com
- Market Failure. (2015) In *AmosWeb Encyclonomic WEB*pedia*. Retrieved on September 28, 2016 from http://www.amosweb.com/cgi-bin/awb_nav.pl?s=wpd
- Organization. (2012). In *Business Dictionary*. Retrieved September 28, 2016 from <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/organization.html>
- Riegler, A. (2012). Constructivism. In L. L'Abate (ed.), *Paradigms in theory construction* (pp. 235-255), New York: Springer. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4614-0914-4_13
- Robbins, S.P., Coulter, M., Sidani, Y., & Jamali, D. (2011). *Management: Arab World Edition*. London, England: Pearson.
- Segal, I. (1999). Complexity and renegotiation: A foundation for incomplete contracts. *Review of Economic Studies*, 57-82.
- Srinivas, H. (n.d.). *How the World Bank works with non-governmental organizations*. The World Bank, retrieved from <http://www.gdrc.org/ngo/wb-define.html>
- Taylor, C.W. (Ed.). (1959). *The third University of Utah research conference on the identification of scientific talent* (pp. 162–174). Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press. (Reprinted in: Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential tension* (pp. 225–239). Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press).
- Tejvan Pettinger (2015). *Government failure*. Economics Help, retrieved from <http://www.economicshelp.org/microessays/market-failure/government-failure/>
- Cooperation. (2016, May 26). In *Boundless.com*. Retrieved 12 October 2016 from <https://www.boundless.com/sociology/textbooks/boundless-sociology-textbook/social-interaction-5/types-of-social-interaction-51/cooperation-319-8261/>
- United Nations Industrial Development Organization. (2015). *Definition of corporate social responsibility*. Retrieved from <http://www.unido.org/en/what-we-do/trade/csr/case-studies.html>
- United Nations Rule of Law. (2015). *Definition of NGO*. Retrieved from <http://www.unrol.org/article.aspx>

Yin, R. (2004). Case study methods, revised draft. To appear in 3rd edition of *Complementary methods for research in education*. Washington, DC: American Educational Research Association, in press.

Zickmund, W.G., Babin, B.J., Carr, J.C. & Griffin, M. (2010). *Business research methods* (8th Ed.). Montreal, Quebec, Canada: South-Western.

APPENDIX
INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Interview 1: Cénacle de la Lumière on April 17, 2014 with Mr. Raphi Keypikian

1. What does your Organization do?
2. In order to reach the above objective, do you have any cooperation with the Government?
3. What does this contract state?
4. Other than the Ministry of Social Affairs, do you have any cooperation with the government?
5. Do you have cooperation with any other organization?
6. Do you have any cooperation with any other Business or Corporation?
7. Is this cooperation with the above mentioned parties helping you and facilitating your work? Or is it complementary to your work
8. Do you have anything else you would like to add?
9. Are these relations in any way preventing your work? Or is the relation always being positive between you?

Interview 2: Lebanese Physically Handicapped Union with Mr. Jihad Ismael on
April 24, 2014

1. What type of work does your organization do?
2. So mainly, you focus on building a better society through having equality among all its members and through having all necessities to handicapped people in all buildings.
3. In order to reach the goals, do you have any relation / cooperation with the government?
4. How about cooperation with another NGO or a business / corporation?
5. Are these relations improving your work? Or are they restricting it?
6. Can you give me an example?
7. Is any of the said cooperation formal?
8. So, without the cooperation, will the work be done?

Dona N. Nakhle

Mobile: +961 3 926856/ Email: dona_nakhle@hotmail.com

Work Experience

Chedid Re Brokerage, Baabda, Lebanon

Jan 12 - Present

One of the biggest International Reinsurance Brokerage Companies that operates in different countries in the Middle East and the Gulf Region

Position: Senior Quality Control Officer / Marine, Life and Casualty Department

Job Description:

- Issuing Cover Notes, Endorsements, and Declarations for Life, Marine and Casualty Files.
- Issuing Debit and Credit Notes for Insurance and Reinsurance Companies.
- Checking closings received from clients and issuing the necessary for their correction is case discrepancies appear.
- Sending all Credit and Debit notes to accounting on time.

Education

Middle East University, (MEU), Sabtiye, Lebanon

Oct 11 – Sept 15

Masters of Business Administration – Management

Notre Dame University (NDU), Zouk Mosbeh, Lebanon

Oct 07 – June 11

Major: BBA / Finance

Antonine Sisters School

Oct 92 – July 07

Lebanese Bacculaureate Part 2 in Sociology & Economics

Certificates

Chartered Insurance Institute (CII)

Oct 14 – Present

- Award in General Insurance (W01)

Certificate in Leadership and Management

Aug 11 – Feb 12

Lebanese Red Cross – Jounieh Sector

Certificate in Team Work

Aug 12 and Aug 13

JKCC International Consultancy and Training

PERSONAL information & Skills

- Marital Status: Single / Place and Date of Birth: U.A.E – July 01, 1989
- Red Cross Volunteer during the period from February 2009 until February 2012
- Languages Proficiency: Arabic / Fluent – English / Fluent – French / Average
- Proficient in Microsoft Office Applications; Word, Excel, PowerPoint, Outlook...
- Highly organized, detail oriented, resourceful and energetic with an ability to work in harmony with people of different backgrounds.
- Organize workloads, set priorities, well used to different kinds of pressures and able to deliver multi tasks during different short deadlines
- Hardworking, honest, team player and great with customers and employees. Most of all, I am reliable and will always be present when expected